

Section 1: General information	Organization acronym: example
Name	Lien Reyserhove
Email	lien.reyserhove@inbo.be
Organization	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
Role in organization	data steward
Purpose of the field management	maintain daily rat control
Section 2: Field management scope	
Taxonomic scope: which species are managed	<i>Heracleum mantegazzianum</i> , <i>Rodentia</i> , <i>macrophytes</i>
Geographical scope	examples: Flanders, Wallonia, Belgium
Temporal scope: start year	2010
Temporal scope: end year (if ongoing, please indicate as such)	ongoing
Section 3: Content and structure	
Name of the application	
Geographical description of the management unit	polygons, point locations, transects, etc.
Description of the management methods	mechanical removal, hand picking, trapping, chemical application, etc.
If possible, specify the details of the registered management methods	description of trap types, chemical compounds used, materials used, etc.
The variables considered to report on management impact	% m2 removal, degree of infestation, etc.
The variables considered to report on non-target effects of management	bycatch, impact on non-target species or the environment, etc.
The variables considered to report on management effort	time spent, people deployed, etc.
Other variables considered?	
Section 4: Methods and technology	
Which technology is used to enter field management data. If a smartphone application or web interface is used, please specify the name	field form, smartphone application, software with a web interface, etc.
Is it an open source software?	yes, no
If not, specify the costs for the license	cost in euro
Where are field management data stored	database hosted on the server of your organization, database in the cloud, spreadsheets, etc.
What is the typical time lag between actions in the field and data availability to the organization?	1 day, 2 weeks, immediately, etc.
Can you give a description of the dataflow starting from the reporting in the field to the storage of those data within your organisation?	data entry using smartphone application --> upload to local computer --> database in the cloud
Do you have any material illustrating the data flow available? If yes, could you please share it with us?	information sheets, presentation, etc.
Section 5: Standards and sharing	
Are the field management data compliant with international standards? If yes, which ones?	dates (ISO format), location (ISO country code), etc.
Who has access to the management data?	only field managers, openly available, etc.
Are the management data openly published in an (inter)national repository?	Zenodo, Geoloket, GBIF
If yes, what is the time lag between reporting management in your system and the publication of these data?	1 day, 1 month, etc.
If not, are there legal constraints for sharing the management data openly?	yes, no
Section 6: Roadmap to improved field management reporting system	
Are you satisfied with the field management system you are using?	
Is there any prospect of your organisation adopting alternative management reporting tools?	
Which features or aspects would you like to change?	